

Notebook 3

Group:

1. Access the Technological Mediation Cards using the QR code below

2. Use the Cards to explore different perspectives and stimulate the creation of innovative solutions.

3. After exploring the Technological Mediation Cards, record in the corresponding field the ideas developed for each type of relation.

NOTE: The speculative solutions do not need to be incorporated into the final design, but they are essential for fostering new possibilities.

Describe the Technological Solution. It is worth noting that using the results from the mediation cards is not mandatory.

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Activity Flow

Describe how the solution maximizes positive and desirable implications and minimizes negative ones.

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implication ID *Solution for the implication*
